

In-situ alloying of Ti-Nb-Sn samples by Laser Additive Manufacturing: phase stability and non-isothermal heat treatment

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Abstract

Powder bed fusion - laser beam (PBF-LB) typically relies on pre-alloyed metallic powders, allowing for precise control over their composition, morphology, and particle size, which are achieved through advanced atomization methods. In-situ alloying in PBF-LB presents a cost-effective solution for developing non-commercial alloys, avoiding complex and costly pre-alloying procedures. One critical aspect to consider when employing in-situ alloying in PBF-LB is achieving microstructure homogenization, which can be influenced by the presence of elemental particles and uneven distribution of alloying elements. In this work, a Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn (wt.%) alloy was produced by PBF-LB using elemental powder blends under two representative processing conditions to elucidate process–microstructure–property relationships. Processing with low laser power and high scanning speed resulted in chemically heterogeneous microstructures containing unmelted Nb particles. These particles locally stabilized the β phase, induced microstructural gradients, and promoted ω -phase precipitation. In contrast, optimized processing conditions yielded a more homogeneous microstructure with columnar prior- β grains and suppressed ω -phase formation. The optimized condition exhibited a high as-built ultimate compressive strength of approximately 1355 MPa, exceeding values reported for cast Ti-Nb-Sn alloys. Differential scanning calorimetry revealed overlapping transformation events consistent with the $\beta \rightarrow \omega_{iso} \rightarrow \beta_0 \rightarrow \alpha$ sequence, with reduced thermal activity upon reheating, indicating partial completion of phase transformations. After DSC thermal cycling, only α and β phases were detected. A systematic gradient in α -plate thickness developed during heat treatment and was attributed to differential oxygen uptake, demonstrating a potential pathway for spatial control of microstructure and mechanical properties. This effect was suppressed in samples containing unmelted Nb particles due to strong local β -phase stabilization. These findings highlight the critical role of processing parameters in controlling Nb dissolution, phase stability, and microstructural uniformity in in-situ alloyed Ti-Nb-Sn systems processed by PBF-LB.

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1. Introduction

The demand for improved load-bearing devices for orthopedic implants has driven the development of novel titanium alloys, particularly metastable β Ti alloys. The use of Ti alloys is supported by their excellent corrosion resistance, high biocompatibility, and unique mechanical properties [1, 2]. The addition of β -stabilizing solutes such as Nb to Ti, combined with appropriate heat treatments, leads to the formation of stable and metastable phases, including hexagonal (α') or orthorhombic (α'') phases [3]. A higher content of β -stabilizing elements suppresses the martensitic transformation, enabling β phase retention at room temperature. However, when the β phase is retained on quenching under metastable conditions, the ω phase is likely to be precipitated [3]. Suitable heat treatments applied to a metastable β -Ti alloy result in notable enhancement of the mechanical strength, which is caused by α -phase precipitation into the β phase matrix [4, 5].

Alloys in the Ti-Nb system have been extensively studied in recent years because of the highly effective role of Nb as a β -stabilizing element and its strong biocompatibility [6–8]. Therefore, several metastable β -type Ti alloys developed as biomaterials now include Nb in their composition. Two notable examples are the TNTZ (Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr wt.%) and TNZT (Ti-35Nb-7Zr-5Ta wt.%) alloys, which are already used in orthopedic implant devices [9–11]. In these alloys, Nb acts as the primary β -stabilizing element, making a significant contribution to the β phase retention under metastable conditions. Nevertheless, the retained β phase can lead to the athermal ω phase precipitation, increasing the elastic modulus. However, this can be mitigated by the adding Sn [12–14]. One of the pioneering studies that experimentally correlated the elastic modulus with composition in Ti-Nb-Sn alloys was conducted by Ozaki et al. [15]. They observed that the minimum elastic modulus is achieved when the athermal ω phase is suppressed. Furthermore, the authors reported that the addition of Sn to Ti-Nb alloys inhibits the ω phase transformation, thus leading to a reduction in Young’s modulus. In another investigation, Moraes et al. determined that the Sn addition to the Ti-30Nb alloy resulted in a decreased elastic modulus [16].

In the past few years, the processing of Ti alloys has undergone significant changes due to advancements in additive manufacturing (AM) technology. The AM techniques allow the production of an entirely new class of products with complex geometries and compositions using a layer-by-layer deposition method [17–19]. Among the various AM techniques, powder bed fusion - laser beam (PBF-LB), selectively welds metallic powder particles using a laser beam source [20]. Generally, PBF-LB technology relies on processing costly, pre-alloyed powders with specific compositions, morphologies, and dimensions. The availability of these metallic powders is limited to only a few compositions, making the atomization of a particular metallic alloy an expensive procedure. An effective approach to overcome restrictions regarding the availability of pre-alloyed powders is the use of in-situ alloying AM, in which the feedstock is obtained from elemental powder blends and the alloy synthesis occurs during the deposition [21, 22]. In-situ alloying is effective in reducing complexities concerning the use of pre-alloyed powder and expands the composition range of resulting alloys. Nonetheless, in-situ alloying requires a detailed evaluation of processing conditions, particularly the selection of suitable processing parameters, such

as scanning speed and laser beam power, to avoid particles that were not melted and/or mixed.

The in-situ alloying procedure is especially challenging when dealing with alloying elements having vastly different melting points, as in the case of Ti-Nb-Sn alloys, with melting points of Ti (1,677 °C), Nb (2,467 °C) and Sn (231.9 °C) [23]. An additional difficulty comes from the Sn boiling point (2,625 °C), which is close to the Nb melting point [23]. Hence, the processing parameters must be precisely selected to melt the higher melting point alloying elements while preventing the loss of those elements with low boiling points. In a recent study, Cheng et al. utilized PBF-LB technique to fabricate porous scaffolds from a Ti-33Nb-4Sn (wt.%) alloy [24]. They employed partially spherical Ti, Nb, and Sn powders, relatively moderate laser power, and a high scanning speed. According to this report, the resulting samples exhibited the retained β phase, with no evidence of martensite formation. In contrast, Semboshi et al. assessed the impact of adding Sn to Ti-35Nb on the microstructure and found that Ti-35Nb and Ti-35Nb-3Sn, when quenched from the β phase field, exhibited α'' martensite within the prior β grain [25].

In-situ alloyed samples often suffer from non-melted particles of the metal with the highest melting point, in this case Nb, and thus chemically heterogeneous material. Subsequent heat treatments at high temperatures can promote chemical homogenization and may also trigger phase transformations. Therefore, detailed analyses performed during and after heat treatments are a valuable tool for assessing microstructural features of in-situ AM Ti alloys [26–28].

Recently, Rodrigues, J. F. et al. [29] successfully synthesized a Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn (wt.%) alloy using the PBF-LB process with in-situ alloying. The study explored a wide range of scanning speeds and laser power settings to optimize the trade-off between porosity and the presence of unmelted Nb particles. As a result, the authors identified a new processing window defined by lower scanning speeds and medium laser power, which yielded improved alloy quality. For instance, a homogeneous microstructure was obtained at 200 W and 100 mm/s, while processing at 100 W and 300 mm/s resulted in a heterogeneous microstructure with a high fraction of unmelted Nb particles. However, the influence of post-processing heat treatments on specimens with identical compositions but distinct as-built microstructures, namely, chemically homogeneous and heterogeneous states, with and without unmelted Nb particles, was not addressed. The present study aims to bridge this gap by providing a more comprehensive characterization of the alloy. Specifically, it extends beyond the processing window definition to include an in-depth analysis of the microstructure, physical properties, and also heat-treated in situ AM Ti-Nb-Sn samples obtained using different processing parameters.

2. Experimental procedure

The in-situ alloying additive manufacturing of Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn (wt.%) samples was performed using an OmniSint-160 (OmniTek Tecnologia) machine equipped with Yb:YAG fiber laser, wavelength of 1070 nm, spot size of 80 μm and maximum laser power of 400 W. The samples were built under a high-purity Ar dynamic atmosphere, with the argon flux set to maintain an oxygen content of less than 800 ppm. The samples were prepared from gas atomized Ti-cp (grade 2 - GE Additive's AP&C, Canada), Nb (99.8% - Suoyi Group Co., China) and Sn (99.9% - Suoyi Group Co., China) powders. The Ti, Nb, and Sn powders were mixed for 2 hours under an Ar atmosphere in an eccentric rotary mixer at 140 rpm. All the specimens were deposited on a Ti-6Al-4V alloy building platform using two different sets of parameters: condition I and condition II, which were based on the

previous study of our group [29], as indicated in Table 1. In both experiments, the hatch space of 80 μm and layer thickness of 30 μm were selected, whereas the laser scanning direction was rotating by 67° at every deposited layer, producing cylindrical samples of 5 mm in diameter and 7 mm in length.

Table 1: Power and scanning speed that were used during the alloy deposition.

Condition	Power (W)	Scanning speed ($mm.s^{-1}$)
I	100	300
II	200	100

The interstitial O and N contents were measured in a Leco TC400 analyzer, and the alloying element content was determined by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) in a Shimadzu EDX7000 instrument. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses were conducted using two SEM equipments: a Zeiss model EVO MA 15, equipped with backscatter electron (BSE) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detectors, and a Thermo Fisher Scientific model Quanta 650 FEG, equipped with BSE and the electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) detectors. The EBSD maps were generated using ATEX analysis software [30]. The samples obtained were polished and etched with a Kroll’s solution (aqueous solution containing 3 vol% of HNO_3 P. A. and 6 vol% of HF P. A.). X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were performed from 30° to 90° (2θ) in a PANalytical X’Pert diffractometer using CuK_α radiation, 45 kV, and 35 mA. Compared to the previous study [29], the samples analyzed in this work were fabricated with smaller build diameter, and the XRD patterns were collected along a different orientation relative to the building direction. These differences are relevant for interpreting the phase evolution and for comparison with the earlier results.

Phase transformations were investigated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a Netzsch STA 449 F3 instrument. DSC curves were obtained in two thermal cycles from 50 °C to 1,000 °C at heating/cooling rate of 10.0 °C.min⁻¹ and an argon flux of 50 mL min⁻¹. The sample microstructure was also evaluated by SEM after the 2nd DSC thermal cycle. Nano hardness tests were performed using a CSM Instruments, which applied a maximum load of 50 mN and was equipped with a Berkovich diamond indenter. The nanoindentation tests also provided the Young’s modulus of individual specimens. Cylindrical compression specimens, measuring (3.33 ± 0.03 mm) in height and (1.67 ± 0.02 mm) in diameter, were machined using electrical discharge machining (EDM). The compression tests were performed on an EMIC DL2000 universal testing machine at a strain rate of 5 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹. Each sample underwent three tests to confirm reproducibility.

3. Results and Discussion

The interstitial content of oxygen (O) and nitrogen (N) in the Ti, Nb, and Sn powders, as well as in the as-built samples, is shown in Table 2. Considering that the sample incorporates N and O in the PBF-LB manufacturing, the as-built samples exhibited higher levels of O and N than the raw Ti powder. Furthermore, sample II presented a higher O and N content than sample I. This result was expected since sample II was processed at a lower scanning speed and higher laser power.

Table 2: Oxygen and Nitrogen contents in the raw powders and the as-built samples.

Sample	O (wt.%)	N (wt.%)
Ti powder	0.158 ± 0.001	0.016 ± 0.006
Nb powder	0.317 ± 0.037	0.034 ± 0.003
Sn powder	0.234 ± 0.015	0.0011 ± 0.0002
As-built sample I ^[29]	0.277 ± 0.001	0.044 ± 0.006
As-built sample II ^[29]	0.349 ± 0.035	0.129 ± 0.042

The chemical composition of the Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn samples was determined using XRF, as shown in Table 3. A decrease in Nb and Sn contents was observed compared to the nominal composition in both samples. Regarding laser power parameters, too low power may not achieve complete melting of Nb particles, while too high power can cause evaporation of Sn, potentially increasing porosity. A lower Sn content was expected in Sample II, which was processed with higher laser power and slower scanning conditions that can promote Sn evaporation.

Table 3: Alloying elements content in the Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn at conditions I and II.

Sample	Ti (wt.%)	Nb (wt.%)	Sn (wt.%)
As-built sample I	Balance	24.49 ± 0.27	2.29 ± 0.01
As-built sample II	Balance	27.10 ± 2.50	2.10 ± 0.20

The microstructural behavior of Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn samples was characterized in both the as-built condition and after thermal cycles during DSC. Fig. 1 shows SEM image and EDS composition maps that were obtained from the Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn alloy at condition I. A considerable amount of Nb particles is noted, while Sn is equally distributed into the Ti matrix. Nb has a higher melting point, which requires a higher energy density for its melting and dissolution. The brighter regions in sample I correspond to areas with high concentrations of Nb, while the dark regions exhibit a high Ti content. These undissolved particles are dispersed into a Ti-rich matrix.

Figure 1: (a) SEM-BSE image and EDS composition maps of the in-situ alloyed AM sample I; and (b) SEM-BSE image and EDS line scan showing the composition variation near a Nb particle.

Fig. 1-b shows an EDS line scan analysis that was conducted near a Nb particle in an SEM-BSE image, revealing significant insights into the as-built sample I microstructure. The Sn composition profile did not exhibit substantial chemical changes compared to the Nb and Ti ones, whose chemical variations played a major role in phase formation. Considering the composition profile combined with the microstructure image, the presence of a diffusion zone surrounding the Nb-rich particle indicates that this element partially diffused during the deposition process, which promoted Nb-rich regions around the particle. The high Nb content leads to the formation of a metastable β phase upon rapid cooling, as provided by the AM process. Phase stability in metallic materials is frequently correlated with valence electron density reported in the literature [31, 32]. This relationship has been extended to Ti alloys through the application of the e/a ratio, the number of valence electrons per atom, to predict phase formation. In Ti–Nb alloys, the stability of the β phase increases as the e/a ratio approaches 4.20 [33, 34], whereas a reduction in this ratio favors the formation of orthorhombic and hexagonal martensitic phases. The e/a ratio was locally calculated along the EDS line scan, as shown in Fig. 1-d, and the predicted phase distribution is in excellent agreement with the morphological features observed around the Nb particle. In the vicinity of the Nb particle, the higher Nb content results in elevated e/a values, consistent with β phase stability. With increasing distance from the particle, the Nb content gradually decreases, leading to the appearance of mixed $\alpha'' + \beta$ regions. Further away, finely dispersed orthorhombic martensitic α'' laths become predominant. Finally, an additional decrease in Nb content and, a consequent decrease in the e/a ratio promotes the formation of thick plates of hexagonal martensite, referred to as the α' phase.

In as-built sample I, the laser power and scanning speed were insufficient to melt the

Nb particles and produce a homogeneous alloy. In fact, the heterogeneity was useful for making correlations between the alloy composition and phase stability. On the other hand, sample II processing was designed to achieve a more homogeneous condition by increasing the laser power and reducing the scanning speed.

Fig. 2 shows the obtained microstructure at as-built sample II, which induced a significant reduction in the amount of undissolved Nb particles (≈ 0.1 vol.%). Therefore, experimental condition II, with a higher laser power and lower scanning speed than condition I, achieved a higher temperature and increased the convection flux in the melt pool; as a result, the microstructural homogeneity was improved. Nonetheless, this second condition was also associated with a higher Sn loss, as previously discussed, cf. Table 3. Even though the second condition improved the alloy homogeneity, a low fraction of undissolved Nb particles can be detected at lower magnifications as seen in Fig. 2-b. Furthermore, martensitic plates of the α'' phase in the β phase matrix were detected at higher magnifications, as shown in Fig. 2-c. Additionally, Fig. 2-d reveals a cellular/dendritic microstructure, a typical feature of PBF-LB processed Ti alloys [35]. Therefore, at condition II, the sample presented the β and α'' phases, but in contrast to condition I, no evidence of α' phase was found. It is worth noting that in a previous study [29], where samples were analyzed in distinct regions (top and middle), precipitation of the α phase was detected in the middle region. This region corresponds to areas with a lower Nb content and is associated with the darker contrast observed Fig. 2-a.

Figure 2: (a) SEM-BSE image and EDS composition maps of an in-situ alloying AM sample at condition II, (b) and SEM by secondary electrons detector and (c) from an in-situ alloying additively manufactured sample at condition II.

Fig. 3 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples processed under condition I and II. For condition I, only peaks corresponding to the martensitic α'' phase, the ω , and the metastable β phase were detected. The precipitation of the ω phase primarily attributed to the unmelting of Nb, which caused a lower β stabilization effect. In this

case, the Sn addition alone is insufficient to effectively suppress ω -phase formation. On the other hand, the sample processed under condition II exhibits diffraction peaks associated with the β , α'' , and $\alpha'\backslash\alpha$ phases, in agreement with the microstructural observations shown in Fig. 2. The weak peaks related to $\alpha'\backslash\alpha$ are more likely associated with the α -phase, formed as a result of an in-situ heat treatment, as already reported in [29], rather than with the α' martensite. Under this condition, two main factors contribute to the absence of the ω -phase: (i) more effective Nb dissolution, which enhances β -phase stabilization, and (ii) the higher temperature during processing, which favors α -phase precipitation over ω -phase formation. Additionally, it is also noted that the β phase peaks presented a greater peak broadening at condition I than at condition II, which may be explained by the overlap of β -phases and pure Nb particles, being both BCC structures.

Figure 3: XRD patterns from samples at conditions I and II showing the retained metastable β phase, α' and α'' martensitic phases, as illustrated in Fig. 1-b and Fig. 2b-c.

The EBSD results are presented in Fig. 4. The image quality (IQ) (Fig. 4a-b) maps indicate that both as-built sample I and sample II consist predominantly of α'' martensite. Moreover, as-built sample I (Fig. 4-c) exhibits a greater presence of the BCC phase (14.31 %), which may be attributed to unmelted Nb particles, a higher cooling rate [36], and a combination of process parameters, such as a higher beam scanning speed and the lowest energy density, resulting in an incomplete transformation to α'' . In contrast, as-built sample II shows an almost exclusive predominance of the α'' phase, with the lowest BCC phase content (2.67 %) compared to sample I (Fig. 4-d). This suggests more controlled manufacturing conditions and potentially improved suitability for applications requiring structural stability and predictable mechanical properties. These findings are consistent with the previous SEM analysis (Fig. 1-b and Fig. 2-c) and XRD results (Fig. 3). As shown in Fig. 4e-f, both samples develop columnar prior- β grain structures along the build direction.

Figure 4: EBSD results for the as-built conditions along the build-up direction (BD): (a,b) Image quality (IQ) maps, (c,d) phase maps superimposed on IQ, indicating the distribution of BCC and α'' phases, and (e,f) Inverse Pole Figure (IPF) maps combined with IQ for as-built samples I and II, respectively. Phase fractions were calculated from EBSD maps after filtering for CI > 0.1 and normalized to indexed points only (sum = 100 %) [37].

The engineering stress–strain curves from the compression tests are presented in Fig. 5. As-built sample II exhibits a higher average ultimate strength (σ_u) of 1303 ± 117 MPa compared to as-built sample I, which shows a σ_u of 1142 ± 22 MPa. Conversely, the average strain at rupture (ε) of both samples is statistically comparable, with values of 32.5 ± 2.6 % for as-built sample I and 29.7 ± 2.2 % for as-built sample II. The lower σ_u observed in as-built sample I may be attributed to the presence of un-melted Nb particles, as seen in Fig. 1 [38, 39]. Additionally, this behavior may also be influenced by the higher oxygen content in as-built sample II, which tends to increase the σ_u [40–43].

The mechanical testing results indicate that the PBF-LB process significantly enhances the mechanical performance of the Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn alloy when compared to traditional casting techniques. This is consistent with the findings of Moraes et al. [16], who fabricated Ti-30Nb-XSn alloys (X = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 wt.%) using an arc furnace with a non-consumable tungsten electrode. Notably, the ultimate strength achieved in as-built sample II (1355 MPa) surpasses that of cast alloys across various Sn contents, underscoring the superior performance afforded by AM.

Figure 5: Engineering stress-strain curves of compression tests for as-built sample I and sample II.

Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn samples are expected to constitute a near- β Ti alloy, and when subjected to quenching from 1,000 °C, their microstructure is composed of martensite and retained β phases [44]. Furthermore, the formation of a metastable microstructure is expected due to the high cooling rate inherent to the PBF-LB process, as demonstrated in the previous section. The heterogeneous microstructures found in this study exhibit a combination of α' (only for as-built sample I) and α'' martensitic phases, along with metastable β phases. Considering their metastable characteristic, these phases may be transformed on heating, which can be detected by DSC. The as-built samples I and II were evaluated during two thermal cycles by DSC on heating, as presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: (a) DSC curves of samples that were built under conditions I and II, on heating at first and second thermal cycles.

On the heating cycle of sample I and sample II, an endothermic peak associated with the reverse martensitic transformation ($\alpha'' \rightarrow \beta$) was expected to be detected around

250 °C, as suggested by Bönisch et al. [45]. However, no such peak was detected as seen in Fig. 6-a.

Fig. 6-a highlights a shaded temperature range (325-615 °C) in which both processing conditions (I and II) show a series of superimposed exothermic and endothermic events that cannot be clearly resolved. According to Bonisch, the expected reaction sequence in the Ti-30Nb system is: $\beta \rightarrow \omega_{iso} \rightarrow \beta_0 \rightarrow \alpha$. Although further heating should drive the α phase back to β , this reverse transformation was not clearly observed in the DSC curve. In the second heating cycle the intensity of the thermal events is markedly reduced for both conditions, indicating partial completion or modification of those reactions during the first cycle.

For the sample processed under condition I, an additional broad endothermic event appears in the green-demarcated zone between ≈ 785 °C and ≈ 960 °C. This feature may reflect $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation in Ti-rich regions and/or oxidation occurring during the experiment. Unmelted Nb particles in condition I produce local Ti-rich zones: while pure Ti typically transforms at ≈ 882 °C, the residual Nb in these Ti-rich regions tends to lower the transformation temperature, whereas any incorporated oxygen (an α -stabilizer) raises the β -transus. The net result of these competing effects (Nb-driven β -stabilization versus O-driven α -stabilization) is a broad endothermic interval. On the second heating of sample I, the same endothermic event is present but with reduced intensity and shifted to a lower temperature, consistent with a decreased fraction of Ti-rich regions and further Nb enrichment of the remaining regions, which stabilizes the β phase and lowers the transition temperature. By contrast, the DSC curve for sample II shows no distinct peak attributable to Ti-rich phase transformation, a consequence of the higher compositional homogeneity in that specimen.

The samples that went through the thermal cycles were evaluated by SEM and XRD, and were labeled here as the DSC heat-treated condition. Fig. 7 shows the XRD patterns from DSC heat-treated samples I and II. It was observed only peaks referring to α and β phases without the presence of other metastable phases. Moreover, the α phase peaks are more intense in sample II than in sample I, indicating a larger α -phase fraction in sample II. This behavior is consistent with the SEM observations: undissolved Nb particles remaining in sample I locally stabilize the β phase, thereby reducing α -phase precipitation during cooling.

Figure 7: XRD patterns from DSC heat treated Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn samples that were built at conditions I and II.

Fig. 8 presents the SEM-BSE micrograph and EDS composition maps from the DSC heat-treated sample that was built at condition I. The heat treatment applied during the DSC experiment promoted diffusion around the Nb particles, but it was insufficient to fully dissolve them. Fig. 1-b showed that the as-built sample I presented Nb particles in a β phase matrix, accompanied by martensitic α' and α'' phases. In contrast to the previous condition, the DSC heat-treated sample did not present the martensitic phases, but the α -phase instead, as expected. The EDS maps demonstrate that the α phase precipitates exhibit a low Nb content, as their formation leads to the rejection of Nb into the β phase. The distribution of Sn within the microstructure appears to be uniform. Fig. 8-b displays an SEM image at a higher magnification around a particle (bright region), whose composition is almost pure Nb, in the DSC heat-treated Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn sample I. Additionally, it's also noted that two thermal cycles until 1000 °C promoted a limited diffusion of Nb, since the size of the unmelted particles is still similar to the as-built samples.

Figure 8: (a) SEM-BSE micrograph and EDS composition maps of an in-situ additively manufactured Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn sample at condition I after DSC analysis, and (b) showing diffusion zones around Nb particles and α phase precipitation.

Table 4 shows the mean chemical composition that was determined by EDS point analysis at several regions of the identified phases. The gray region in Fig. 8-b is the β phase that was stabilized by a high content of Nb (45.6 ± 5.6) wt.%, which was available around the particle. The α phase (black regions) is composed by a very lower Nb content of (10.4 ± 1.0) wt.%. In addition, α and β phases had almost the same content of Sn. Nonetheless, the standard deviations of the β phase composition indicated that a chemical gradient is still present since the Nb particles were not completely dissolved.

Table 4: Average composition of the phases that were identified in Fig. 8-b.

Phase	Ti (wt.%)	Nb (wt.%)	Sn (wt.%)
α	86.5 ± 1.0	10.4 ± 1.0	3.0 ± 0.2
β	52.0 ± 4.9	45.6 ± 5.6	2.4 ± 0.7

Fig. 9 shows an SEM-BSE micrograph and EDS composition maps of a DSC heat-treated Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn sample that was built at condition II. The composition maps reveal a microstructure with no evidence of undissolved Nb particles. Furthermore, the EDS maps indicate that the α phase precipitates contain a lower Nb content than the β matrix, whereas Sn is homogeneously distributed throughout the alloy.

The microstructure consists of α plates precipitated within the β matrix, with a noticeable variation in plate thickness across the sample, as shown in the SEM-BSE image in Fig. 9 (left). This microstructural gradient is attributed to differential oxygen uptake during the thermal cycle. The region in contact with the Al_2O_3 pan was less exposed to atmospheric oxygen and experienced minimal interaction with the surrounding environment, resulting in lower oxidation. In contrast, the top surface, being more directly exposed to the atmosphere, underwent increased oxygen uptake. Since oxygen is a strong α -stabilizing element, this enhanced oxidation promoted the stabilization and growth of thicker α plates. Consequently, the α -plate thickness increases progressively from the bottom to the top of the sample.

Figure 9: SEM-BSE micrograph and EDS composition maps of an DSC heat-treated Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn sample that was built at condition II.

The presence of oxygen in DSC heat-treated samples can strongly affect the mechanical properties of each phase. The relationship between phase and mechanical properties in Ti-Nb alloys was investigated by Lee et al. [46], and their results suggest that Vickers hardness (H) changes according to the following sequence: $H_{\omega} > H_{\alpha'} > H_{\alpha''} > H_{\beta}$. They also measured the Vickers Hardness of the α phase in Ti-cp samples, in which there is no solid solution effect. Nonetheless, the Vickers hardness is relatively high when the α phase is dispersed into a β phase matrix. Nanoindentation measurements on sample I after the DSC experiment are shown in Fig. 10. The $\alpha + \beta$ region (position 1) presents an elastic modulus of 112 ± 13 GPa and a Vickers hardness of 551 ± 39 HV. The β phase region (position 2), which is formed in the vicinity of a Nb particle, exhibits an elastic modulus of 85 ± 4.7 GPa, along with a Vickers hardness of 302 ± 50 HV. In terms of microscale mechanical behavior, the Nb particles (position 3) exhibit an elastic modulus of (98 ± 11) GPa and a Vickers hardness of 162 ± 33 HV. The elastic modulus value is reasonably consistent with the results reported in the literature. The Vickers hardness of

Nb depends on the oxygen (O) content, the measured Vickers hardness (cf. Table 2) is consistent with the literature [47].

Figure 10: (a) OM micrograph of the DSC heat-treated Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn sample I showing Berkovich indentations, and (b) their respective Vickers hardness and elastic modulus. These values were estimated from different regions of the sample; the indentations in (a) are only illustrative.

Thermal cycling produced distinct responses in the specimens processed under conditions I and II. In condition I, retained unmelted Nb particles generate local compositional and microstructural gradients and act as grain refiners and nucleation sites (Fig. 8). On the other hand, the condition II specimen preserves its columnar prior- β grains after heat treatment but shows a systematic increase in α -plate thickness through the sample, consistent with differential oxygen uptake. This oxygen-driven α -thickening indicates a viable route to tailor local mechanical properties via controlled oxidation, a phenomenon that is suppressed in condition I because Nb particles stabilize the α phase regardless of oxygen content, keeping α plates thinner.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn (wt.%) alloy was in-situ additively manufactured using different processing parameters. The main conclusions that were reported here can be addressed by the following statements:

- The presence of undissolved Nb particles led to composition gradients, which induced the formation of β , α' and α'' phases.
- The compression test results confirm that the PBF-LB process greatly improves the mechanical performance of the Ti-30Nb-2.5Sn alloy, particularly when compared to conventional casting methods.
- The heterogeneous microstructure at condition I results in the occurrence of a broad range of α to β transition (β -transus) in Ti-rich regions.
- The employed thermal cycles were not sufficient to homogenize the microstructure at condition I, but induced the α precipitation at both conditions.
- The thermal cycles promoted insights into the behavior of heterogeneous and homogeneous microstructures of in-situ alloyed samples. In the heterogeneous sample, the undissolved Nb particles promote the formation of solute-rich β phase regions,

while the α phase precipitates far from the Nb particles. In homogeneous samples, a variation in the volume fraction of the α and β phases was observed due to differences in oxygen content and thermal gradients at the top and bottom of the sample during DSC analysis.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16980496> under the CC-BY 4.0 license.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Márcio Sangali: Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing - review & editing. **João Felipe Q. Rodrigues:** Formal analysis; Investigation; Data curation; Writing - review & editing. **Leticia F. Starck:** Formal analysis; Writing - review & editing. **Gilberto V. Prandi:** Formal analysis; Investigation; Writing - review & editing. **Matheus Valentim:** Formal analysis; Writing - review & editing. **Josef Stráský:** Writing - review & editing. **Rodolfo da Silva Teixeira:** Formal analysis; Visualization; Writing - review & editing. **Leandro S. Silva:** Formal analysis; Visualization; Writing - review & editing. **Miloš Janeček:** Funding acquisition; Resources; Writing - review & editing. **Rubens Caram:** Funding acquisition; Resources; Supervision; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing.

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